

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN FRENCH

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Abstract. In this article special characteristics of verbs in French will be expressed.

Key words: verbs, transitive verbs, intransitive verbs, person, movement, item, forms of verbs.

МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ГЛАГОЛОВ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье будут выражены особенности глаголов французского языка.

Ключевые слова: глаголы, переходные глаголы, непереходные глаголы, лицо, движение, предмет, формы глаголов.

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Grammatical categories like transivity, intransivity, positive-negative forms, voice, person, number, moods, tenses are considered special characteristics of verbs. Person (la personne) shows the attitude of the doer of the action to the speaker. The number (le nombre) category indicates whether the possessor is singular or plural through verb forms.

	Singular	Plural	Singular	Plural
1 st person	Je parle	Nous parlons	J'aime	Nous aimons
2 nd person	Tu parles	Vous parlez	Tu aimes	Vous aimez
3 rd person	Il (elle)parle	Ils(elles) parlent	Il(elle)aime	Ils (elles)aiment

Mood (le mode) means the relation of the action understood from the verb to reality, and it expresses that the action is actually being performed and is forced to be performed:

The indicative mood (Indicatif)	The imperative m. (impératif)	The Conditional m. (conditionnel)	The subjunctive mood (Subjonctif)
He is walking. Il marche.	Walk ! Marchez!	He would walk. Il marcherait	He should walk. Qu'il marche

Tense (le temps) indicates the relation of the action to the time of speech. Action indicates that it is performed before, at the same time, or after the time being spoken.

Prèsent de l'indicatif	Passé composé	Futur simple	Imparfait
Il joue He is playing. Elle chante She is singing.	Il a joué He played. Elle a chanté She sang.	Il jouera He is going to play. Elle chantera She is going to sing.	Il jouait He was playing. Elle chantait She was singing.

The voice (la voix) shows the relationship between the doer of the action and the object.
Le professeur a puni cet élève hier Cet élève a été puni par le professeur hier
The teacher punished this pupil yesterday. This pupil was punished by the teacher
yesterday.

La fillette mange des pommes Des pommes sont mangées par la fille
A girl ate the apples. Apples was eaten by a girl.

Personal and impersonal forms of verbs (Les formes personnelles et non personnelles)
Not all forms of verbs have a personal category, therefore there are personal and impersonal forms of verbs. Personal forms of verbs change depending on the person and the act as a linking verb (verbe copule) in a sentence or a noun clause.

Il travaille à l'usine Elle parle bien anglais Elle est devenue
professeur
He works in a factory She speaks English very well She grew up as a
teacher

Je vais à l'école Je parle vite français J'ai besoin d'un stylo
I am going to school I speak fast in French I need a pen

Impersonal forms of verbs (l'infinitif), adjectives (le participe présent, le participe passé, le participe passé composé) and adverbs (gérondif)

The impersonal forms of verbs do not change according to the person, they can act as a different parts of the sentence:

Il pense partir Il aime visiter Il adore lire (infinitive objectless complement)
Je répète les règles étudiées C'est mon film préféré (adjective determiner)
Nous marchons en causant Il marche en chantant (relative adverb)

Transitive and intransitive verbs (Les verbes transitifs et intransitif)

Prendre, lire , écrire – transitive verbs Aller, venir, écrire- intransitive verbs

Verbs that indicate the action affects of the object are called transitive verbs (verbes intrsitifs)

J'ouvre la porte – I opened the door (Action affects the item)

Il reprint son livre – He took his book (Action affects the item)

Verbs that indicate action do not affect the object are called intransitive verbs (verbes intransitifs)

J'ai déjà mangé – I have already eaten (Action does not affect the object)

Il a neigé pendant des jours – It snowed for days (Action does not affect the object)

Transitive verbs are of two types depending on the object they require.

1) Transitive verbs with correct objects:

J'étudie le français. Je l'étudie (Qu'est-ce que j'étudie?)

2) Transitive verbs with an infinitive compliment used with a preposition:

Elle refuse de partir. Elle le refuse (Qu'est-ce qu'elle refuse ?)

Compliments that follow intransitive verbs always come with a preposition:

Je pense à mes examens. Il se sert du dictionnaire

A transitive verb can require both an objectless and with object:

Il donne le stylo à son ami

